

Detoxification and Supporting Supplements:

A Health Medical Approach

Dr. David Render FHP

Research Article

P.O Box 3761

Anaheim, CA 92803

David.d.Render@gmail.com

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Abstract

Detoxification is a need and simple for the body to elimination of unwanted substances. This effects over 300 million Americans and almost 8 billion people in the Earth today. The Living, dead and the unborn. Coughing, elimination of waste, vomiting, and urination and vital organs that expel and filter. The body is a self-healing agent designed to keep the person in homeostasis. This study opens up detoxification practice treatments and concepts in alternative medicine. Detoxification is very helpful to patients and clients suffering from chronic diseases. This can even be mental illness involving the mind, allergies seasonally, anxiety or arthritis and obesity and environmental factors such as cancer. Detoxification therapy is used when conventional medicine is not able to diagnose or treat. A Holistic approach illness/ multiple chemical sensitivity, and fibromyalgia. Sometimes the body can have an intolerance to certain kinds of food to ingest, insomnia, sore throats and sudden weight loss or gain. This is foundationally based that illnesses and diseased caused by accumulation of toxic substances Toxins that are in the body. By understanding the existing toxins and avoidance of new toxins is essential of the person of the healing process. People with the purpose of this study will be able to understand the parts of optimum health to bring wellness to themselves.

Detoxification is a powerful therapy for relief and increase in resistance to disease. The purpose of this study is to present an academic and systematic review of evidence based health and medical synthesize finding from this research for media and television based healing. There is a hope to inform practitioners and patients and those that desire to learn more about medical and holistic care.

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Detoxification (Cleanse and Detox the Body)

Why is detoxification important to the Human body?

The human body is extremely profound in ability, speed, agility, and neurological functions, the being capabilities are beyond impressive. People are not made to store junk and trash for the rest of

our lives with an unhealthy diet involving creams sugars sweets and heavy meats. Balanced diets along with proper exercise is the way to optimum health and wellness. In a holistic viewpoint this will lead to lack of nutrients and vitamins immune system sickness, disease and not the best of performance. If choosing to go by this cleansing method is called detoxification. By detoxing your

body, you help the vital critical internal organs do what they do by cleanse themselves of the toxins, and enable the liver and kidneys to function naturally. This is harmful and foreign substances to the body.

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Thus, you are on a success trip to the restroom. The body's natural way of release of waste and unnecessary substance.

Marketing detox to consumers is a million- dollar business and very lucrative. There are many problems and hazards holistically in life that is not needed in a person's life.

Detox calls the body back into natural alignment and allow homeostasis to come about re balancing the body and repair damage small or large that had taken place. Metals and various toxins build up in the body thus elimination is needed. There are heavy metals that are common yet critical, such as mercury, arsenic, lead, or cadmium, can accumulate in a person's buildup in the body, illness comes about with symptoms mild or severe to the person. What is critical is that the heavy metals are also neurotoxins and dangerous causing damage to brain cells. Obesity, heart disease, ADD, autism have been known to take effect as health problem diseases.

Trusting in your body and listen intently to the sound and feel of what your organs are doing or possibly not doing for health reasons.

- Kidneys will release toxins
- Lungs will cleanse by releasing CO₂
- Skin cleanse is sweating, the skin is an automatic cleanser. Go for a good run or exercise session.
- Intestines remove nutrients from the food you eat and throws away trash.

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Liver and Lung Cleanse (Urination is a cleansing)

- Alcohol the body converts it into sugar, ethanol deriving from fermented sugar with yeast. Alcohol can be depressant to the body and mind to alter various functions. Used as preservative antiseptic or medication.
- Volatile Compound **Volatile** organic **compounds** are **compounds** that have a high vapor pressure and low water solubility. Human made materials from home and building paints, or pharmaceuticals can be problematic to the human body.
- Oxidation Reduction
- Exposure to food ingestion (heavy meats; sweets)
- Medications the body may reject
- Regarding the Outside world Air pollutants the body may clean itself out

Coughing, burping, and throwing up are all mechanisms of the body cleansing.

Even when elimination this can be dangerous to respiratory functions. It is not usually something to be overly concerned about. Many times people don't realize how important the body's natural self-healing bio-mechanism is amazing. There is a great relief of satisfaction, relief, and sometimes pain leaving the body after elimination going to the restroom. This is essential of multiple bowel movements in a week's time and with proper intake of fluids with the right nutrients to bring the body to a healthy balance.

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What kind of things come out or purged?

You may have heard of Phlegm a type of mucus made in your chest. Usually people don't produce noticeable amounts of phlegm unless you are sick with a cold or have some other underlying medical issue. When you cough up phlegm, also known as sputum. You have or will see different colors as well.

Sputum- A mixture of saliva and mucus coughed up from the respiratory tract, typically as a result of infection or other disease and often examined microscopically to aid medical diagnosis.

Colon Cleanse

Cleansing tip: ½ cup Apple juice 2 tablespoons lemon juice and ginger juice great compounds and of

course warm water. This will help detoxify the colon.

When it comes to Medical Detoxification and respiratory help.

Not bad at all you need these vital organs so you can expel trash and non-nutrients from the body. your body is

intelligent, learn to trust your body and listen to your organs from various pains and pressures that are unpleasant.

Irritability and moodiness; even aggression in some situations. Extreme fatigue. Vomiting and nausea. Fever and flu-like symptoms. What is in the body mind soul and spirit comes out. Food and emotions go hand and hand. The old saying goes, “you are what you eat!” So true!

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The human body can be very tricky when it comes to walking this life. You can take in bad air or unhealthy air. Also this can go for foods and as well nutrient deficiency. Holistic Practitioners and Physicians making recommendations toward health and education make sure to consider and take heed. Pay attention to marketed detoxers making vague claims that are deceptive, do your homework and due diligence.

Fatigue and tiredness sets in? Feeling Sluggish

Good diet choices and exercises are extremely important. They are the best choices the body can make. Some other problems that take place patients or clients may be not getting enough sleep or rest.

Eating a balanced diet is vital. When the body is feeling backed up or constipated eating more fiber and fluids. If the problem continues speak with a primary care doctor you trust.

A variety of “detoxification” diets, regimens, and therapies—sometimes called “detoxes” or “cleanses”—have been suggested as ways to get rid of toxins from your body, reduce , or

promote health.

Where in the world can we detox if needed? There are many approaches. These include:

1. Drinking only juices or similar beverages
2. Eating only certain foods
3. Using dietary supplements or other commercial products

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Medical Doctors has found in the lower intestinal with enemas, laxatives, (also called “colonic irrigation” or “colonics”)

Reducing environmental exposures

Sauna treatment

These programs may even be publicized commercially, offered at health centers, or a vicinity of naturopathic treatment.

Governing authorities like the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and Federal Trade Commission (FTC) have taken action against many corporations commerce detox/cleansing merchandise as a result of they contained misappropriated, potentially harmful ingredients; were marketed using false claims that they could treat serious diseases; or in the case of medical devices used for colon cleansing, were marketed for unapproved uses.

- Some juices utilized in “detoxes” and “cleanses” that haven’t been pasteurized or treated in

other ways to kill harmful bacterium will make people sick. The sicknesses are often can be serious in kids, elderly individuals, and people with weakened immune systems.

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- Some juices are made from foods that are high in oxalate, a naturally occurring substance. Two examples of high-oxalate foods are spinach and beets. Drinking large quantities of high-oxalate juice can increase the risk for kidney problems.
- People with diabetes should follow the eating plan recommended by their health care team. If you have diabetes, consult your health care providers before making major changes in your eating habits, such as going on a “detox” diet or changing your eating patterns.
- Diets that severely restrict calories or the types of food you eat usually don’t lead to lasting weight loss and may not provide all the nutrients you need.
- Colon cleansing procedures may have side effects, some of which can be serious. Harmful effects are more likely in people with a history of gastrointestinal disease, colon surgery, severe hemorrhoids uropathy, kidney disease, or heart disease.
- “Detoxification” programs may include laxatives, which can cause diarrhea severe enough to lead to dehydration and electrolyte imbalances.
- Drinking grand quantities of water and herbal tea and not consumption of any food for days in a row could lead on to dangerous solutions imbalances.

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Dietary Supplements What's the Bottom Line?

How much do we know about dietary supplements?

The amount of scientific evidence we have on dietary supplements varies widely—we have a lot of information on some and very little on others.

What do we know about the effectiveness of dietary supplements?

- Studies have found that some dietary supplements may have some benefit, such as melatonin for jet lag, and others may have little or no benefit, such as ginkgo for dementia.
- Supplements you buy from stores or online may differ in important ways from products tested in studies.
- Most research shows that taking multivitamins doesn't result in living longer, slowing cognitive decline, or lowering the chance of getting cancer, heart disease, or diabetes.

What do we know about the safety of dietary supplements?

- Taking a multivitamin is unlikely to pose any health risks.
- Dietary supplements may interact with your medications or pose risks if you have certain medical problems or are going to have surgery.
- Many dietary supplements haven't been tested in pregnant women, nursing mothers, or children.

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- Some products marketed as dietary supplements—promoted mainly for weight loss, sexual enhancement, and bodybuilding—may contain prescription drugs not allowed in dietary supplements or other ingredients not listed on the label. Some of these ingredients may be unsafe.

What Are Dietary Supplements?

It is critical to properly label and give transparency from a product company standpoint with products that can potentially be dangerous or fatal to consumers, Federal law defines dietary supplements as products that:

- You take orally or **orally** PO medical term by mouth (such as a tablet, capsule, powder, or liquid)
- Are made to supplement and/or additive to the body
- Have one or more dietary ingredients, including vitamins, minerals, herbs or other botanicals, amino acids, enzymes, tissues from organs or glands, as being dietary aid.

What Are Herbal Supplements?

Herbal supplements are a kind of dietary supplement the inside containing a few or multiple herbs.

Listed below they are:

Sometimes called botanicals

Made from plants, algae, fungi, or a mixture of those

Sold as teas, extracts, tablets, capsules, powders, or in other forms.

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